

1 **Gene expression signature in the blood for tuberculosis risk.**

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7 Elements in the genetic background likely control progression to disease in the population, suggesting
8 utility for understanding the non-progression signature for discovery of factors that control risk of disease
9 in TB infection. We measured total transcription by RNA-sequencing in the blood in humans all who had
10 been infected with TB, but some of whom failed to proceed to active disease. Non-progressors displayed
11 silencing of *IL31ra* and *IL12rb1*. Interestingly, ISG GBP6 was significantly reduced in non-progressors. We
12 demonstrate here silencing of *Lypd4* in humans infected with TB who fail to progress to disease.

13 Citations

14 1. Zak, D.E., Penn-Nicholson, A., Scriba, T.J., Thompson, E., Suliman, S., Amon, L.M., Mahomed,
15 H., Erasmus, M., Whatney, W., Hussey, G.D. and Abrahams, D., 2016. A blood RNA signature for
16 tuberculosis disease risk: a prospective cohort study. *The Lancet*, 387(10035), pp.2312-2322.

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